

Block Coded Parallel Paths TCM under Fading

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Abstract

Conventional Trellis Coded Modulation (TCM) has been proposed as a power efficient scheme for AWGN channel. However, in a fading channel, the performance of the scheme degrades significantly. Multiple TCM (MTCM) has been proposed as a robust scheme for fading channels. However, MTCM does not perform as a power efficient scheme unless the fading is severe. In a land mobile satellite service environment, fading is intermittent. Therefore, there is need for a scheme which is efficient in both situations (fading and no fading). In this paper, Block Coded Parallel paths TCM (BCP-TCM) scheme is proposed. By encoding the information bits assigned to the parallel paths in TCM, the proposed scheme performs as well as conventional TCM in AWGN and as robust as MTCM in fading.

I. Introduction

With the increasing demand for satellite communications, the research for bandwidth and power efficient modulation systems has become a very active area. In Land Mobile Satellite Service (LMSS), where fading and shadowing are frequently encountered, the system not only needs to achieve high power and bandwidth efficiency, but also should be robust under channel fading and shadowing. In [1,2], multiple trellis coded modulation (MTCM) has been proposed as a robust scheme for Ricean fading. Compared to conventional TCM [3], MTCM is more robust in Ricean fading when fading is severe. However, when fading is light, MTCM does not perform as a power efficient scheme as compared to conventional TCM. Under AWGN, compared to conventional TCM, MTCM scheme degrades by more than 2 dB in power efficiency [4]. On the other hand, conventional TCM, optimally designed for the AWGN channel, is not robust under fading. Since in LMSS environment, fading is intermittent, there is need for a scheme that performs well from no fading to severe fading conditions.

In this paper, a Block Coded Parallel paths TCM (BCP-TCM) scheme is proposed and its performance is analyzed. By encoding the information bits assigned to the parallel paths in the conventional TCM, the proposed scheme performs as well as conventional TCM in AWGN and as robust as MTCM in fading.

II. TCM with Parallel Paths Pre-coded

In conventional TCM scheme, the parallel paths in the trellis diagram constrain the shortest error event to one branch; that is, the length of the shortest error event path equals to one, *i.e.* $L=1$. This length (L) directly determines the performance of the scheme under severely faded channel. Under Rayleigh fading channel, for instance, the symbol error rate performance can be expressed as [1]

$$Pe = C \left(\frac{\bar{E}_s}{N_0} \right)^L \quad (1)$$

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for large \bar{E}_s / N_0 , where \bar{E}_s is the average symbol energy of the

received signal, and N_0 is single side noise power spectral density. Consequently, because of the length of the shortest error event path of one in conventional TCM, the symbol error rate varies only in a

inverse relationship to \bar{E}_s / N_0 . Therefore, conventional TCM is not robust under fading. However, by encoding the information bits assigned to parallel transition paths with a block code (relatively short-length) before trellis coding, these information bits will become robust.

The decoding procedure can be divided into two steps. At first, all the information bits are decoded by the Viterbi decoder. Then, only the information bits assigned to the parallel transitions are decoded by the block decoder. After decoding and error correction, the system performance will depend on the length of nonparallel transitions and the minimum weight of the block code.

4-State Rate 2/3 8PSK TCM with Parallel Bit Block Coded

A typical block diagram of conventional TCM with 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK is shown in Fig.2. From Fig.2, it is obvious that the first information bit is directly mapped to 8PSK without coding. This uncoded information bit corresponds to the parallel transition paths in the trellis diagram shown in Fig.1. If the first information bit is encoded before mapping to 8PSK, this information bit will become robust. The block diagram of this TCM with first information bit block encoded is shown in Fig.3. Since the information bit is block encoded before trellis coding, the information bit rate between first bit and second bit is different. For instance, assuming that the first bit is encoded with (7,4) BCH code, the first information bit rate is 4/7, while the second information bit rate is 1. An input data rate adjuster as well as an output data rate adjuster are needed for coping with this rate difference in the system.

III. BER Performance of 4-State Rate 2/3 8PSK TCM with Parallel Paths Pre-coded

The error in TCM with parallel paths pre-coded can be separated into two parts. One is nonparallel transition error and the other is parallel transition error. Nonparallel transition error occurs when wrong decision is made for the transition nonparallel to the correct transition paths. In the multiple-phase signal set with signal points located on a circle of radius $\sqrt{E_s}$, the shortest Euclidean distance among the nonparallel transition paths in trellis coded 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK equals to

$$d_{non} = \sqrt{\Delta_2^2 + \Delta_1^2 + \Delta_2^2} = 2.14\sqrt{E_s} \quad (2)$$

where Δ_i , $i=1,2$, denotes the free Euclidean distance of 8PSK and QPSK signals respectively and E_s denotes 8PSK signal symbol energy. On the other hand, parallel transition errors happen when the incorrect decision is made for branches parallel to the correct transition paths. In trellis coded 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK, the minimum Euclidean

distance between the parallel transitions is $2\sqrt{E_s}$. Since the information bits assigned to the parallel transition paths are block

coded before trellis coding, the extra coding gain is expected after decoding and error correction.

The error rate performance of the trellis coded signals with nonparallel paths in the presence of additive white Gaussian noise can be well approximated by [5]

$$P_{e\text{non}} = N_{\text{non}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{d_{\text{non}}^2}{4N_0}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where N_{non} denotes the number of signal sequences with distance d_{non} that diverge at any state and remerge at that state after nonparallel transitions, and $\operatorname{erfc}(\cdot)$ is a complementary error function. For parallel transition paths, after error correction with hard decision, the error rate performance in the presence of AWGN is given by

$$P_{e\text{par}} = \frac{K}{N} \sum_{m=1}^n \binom{n}{m} p^m (1-p)^{n-m} \quad (4)$$

where $t = \lfloor \frac{d_{\text{min}}-1}{2} \rfloor$ is the error correction capability of the (n,k) block code. d_{min} is the minimum Hamming distance of the block code, and p is error probability of the trellis coded bits with parallel paths in AWGN, which is approximated as

$$p \approx N_{\text{par}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{d_{\text{par}}^2}{4N_0}} \right) \quad (5)$$

where N_{par} denotes the number of signal sequences with minimum Euclidean distance d_{par} of parallel paths, which diverge at any state and remerge at that state after parallel transitions. The total error performance of trellis coded MPSK in the presence of AWGN is

$$P_e = \operatorname{Pr}\{\text{nonparallel}\} \cdot P_{e\text{non}} + \operatorname{Pr}\{\text{parallel}\} \cdot P_{e\text{par}} \quad (6)$$

For the case of trellis coded 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK with parallel bit encoded by (7,4) BCH code, we have

$$\operatorname{Pr}\{\text{nonparallel}\} = 0.5$$

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$$N_{\text{non}} = 2, N_{\text{par}} = 2$$

$$d_{\text{non}} = 2.14\sqrt{E_s}, d_{\text{par}} = 2\sqrt{E_s}$$

$$d_{\text{min}} = 3$$

$$t = \lfloor \frac{d_{\text{min}}-1}{2} \rfloor = 1, \text{ and } E_s = 1.6E_b$$

then

$$P_e \approx \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{4.585E_s}{4N_0}} + \frac{2^7}{7} \sum_{m=2}^7 \binom{7}{m} \left(\operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{E_s}{N_0}} \right)^m \left(1 - \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{E_s}{N_0}} \right)^{7-m} \quad (7)$$

At high SNR, the first term is dominant, and Eq.(7) can be approximated as

$$P_e \approx \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{4.585E_s}{4N_0}} \approx \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{1.8E_b}{N_0}} \quad (8)$$

For the conventional trellis coded 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK with coherent detection, the BER performance in AWGN is given by[5]

$$P_{\text{TCM}} \approx \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{2E_b}{N_0}} \quad (9)$$

The BER performance of trellis coded 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK with first information bit encoded by (7,4) BCH code degrades by only 0.46dB in AWGN. If (15,11) BCH code is used, $E_s = 1.73E_b$, then the BER performance of proposed scheme will be almost the same as that of conventional TCM scheme in AWGN.

On the other hand, consider TCM in Rayleigh fading channel. Assuming perfect Channel State Information (CSI) and coherent detection, the average error rate is approximately given by

$$P_e = C \left(\frac{\bar{E}_s}{N_0} \right)^{-L} \quad (1)$$

where C is a constant that depends on the distance structure of the code, L is the length of shortest error event path. The length of the nonparallel transition paths in trellis coded 4-state 2/3 8PSK is equal to three, i.e. $L=3$. Therefore, the bit error rate of 4-state TCM with nonparallel paths in Rayleigh fading channel is approximated as

$$P_{\text{TCM}} = C \left(\frac{\bar{E}_s}{N_0} \right)^{-3} \quad (10)$$

For the parallel paths

$$P_{\text{par}} = \frac{K}{N} \sum_{m=1}^n \binom{n}{m} p_f^m (1-p_f)^{n-m} \quad (11)$$

where P_f is error probability of the bits assigned to the parallel paths, which, for high SNR, is given by [5]

$$p_f \approx \left(\frac{4\bar{E}_s}{N_0} \right)^{-1} \quad (12)$$

The bit error rate performance of trellis coded 4-state MPSK with parallel paths with general (n,k) block coding is

$$P_{\text{bf}} = \{\operatorname{Pr}\{\text{nonparallel}\} \cdot P_{\text{non}} + \operatorname{Pr}\{\text{parallel}\} \cdot P_{\text{par}}\} \quad (13)$$

where P_{bf} is the bit error probability in fading channel. Consider 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK TCM with first bit encoded by BCH (7,4) code as an example. At high SNR, higher order terms in Eq.(13) can be ignored, and the bit error rate is approximated as

$$P_{\text{bf}} \approx 0.1 \left(\frac{\bar{E}_s}{N_0} \right)^{-2} \quad (14)$$

The average BER performance of the proposed scheme, if the block code has the ability to correct one error in a code-word, will vary

inversely with the square of \bar{E}_s / N_0 in the Rayleigh fading channel.

Compared to conventional TCM, the proposed scheme is more robust in the fading channel. Computer simulation shows that the proposed scheme has almost the same BER performance under AWGN. If (7,4) BCH code is employed. Under Rayleigh fading channel, the proposed scheme performs as robust as 4-state rate 4/6 trellis coded 8PSK (MTCM)[5] if (7,4) BCH code is employed. The BER performance of the proposed scheme under AWGN and Rayleigh fading channel is shown in Fig.4(a) and Fig.4(b), respectively.

IV. Conclusion

In conventional TCM, parallel transition paths cause degradation in the system performance when fading is severe. When the information bits assigned to those parallel transition branches are coded before TCM encoder, system becomes robust even in severe fading. The proposed scheme performs as well as conventional TCM in AWGN and as robust as MTCM under Rayleigh fading. The trade-off is the small additional bandwidth requirement because of the block code used in the system.

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(a) Trellis diagram of 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK TCM. (b) One of the shortest error event paths in nonparallel transition paths.

Fig.1 Trellis diagram of conventional 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK TCM.

Fig.2 Block diagram of conventional 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK TCM

(a) Transmitter

(b) Receiver

Fig.3 Block diagram of trellis coded 4-state rate 2/3 8PSK with first information bit encoded by (7,4) BCH code.

(a) BER curve under AWGN.

(b) BER curve under Rayleigh fading.

Fig.4 Bit error rate performance of TCM (4-state rate 2/3 8PSK), MTCM (4-state rate 4/6 8PSK) and first information bit BCH (7,4) coded 4-state rate 2/3 TCM under AWGN and Rayleigh fading channels.

* Curve of MTCM is from [4].

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